
CONDITIONS OF SERVICE AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS' JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study examined conditions of service and teachers' support services as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Four research questions guided the study and four null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study is 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 660 teachers (that is, 10% of teachers' population) was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection: Conditions of Service Questionnaire (COSQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ). Face validation was done by three experts while construct validation was carried out with Principal Component Analysis approach. The reliability of the instruments was pilot tested in Enugu State using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient and the average coefficient values of 0.83 for COSQ and 0.87 for TJCQ are considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Simple regression analysis was used for the study. The study revealed that payment of salary ($r=0.773$ $p=0.000$), promotion ($r=0.751$ $p=0.000$), fringe benefits ($r=0.618$ $p=0.000$), recognition ($r=0.524$ $p=0.000$), positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that the honouring of teachers' conditions of service positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that government should improve the monetary reward for teachers to enable them afford their needs. Apart from that, there should be prompt payment of salaries including all allowances accruing to teachers: salaries should be paid regularly as at when due. Also, the practice of owing teachers' salaries for some months or percentage payment should be stopped as that has destroyed teachers' commitment and dedication to work.

Keywords: Condition of service, job commitment, payment of salaries, promotion.

Introduction

Teacher's conditions of service can make or mar their commitment in schools. In this regard, the conditions of service under which teachers discharge their duties can never be neglected because it might have a great influence on their commitment and productivity. Teachers are motivated to show commitment to duty and work closely together for maximum productivity in an environment whose climate is acceptable, lively, adaptable, conducive, supportive and comfortable.

Teachers' job commitment is defined as the strength of a teacher's identification and involvement with the teaching job. It determines whether a person will leave or remain in the teaching profession or not. Kaegon and Okere (2023) defined teachers' job commitment as a psychological state that characterizes a teacher's relationship with his or her profession, and has implications for the decision to remain involved with it. It is the emotional bond between the teacher and the school. Teachers' job commitment is regarded as a power or quality needed to approach stress and change. It includes factors such as honesty, responsibility, and tolerance for fallibility. Teachers' job commitment is of importance as it is associated with greater job effort and involvement, that is, committed employees are less likely to leave their position and display other withdrawal behaviour such as absenteeism. As Ahmed (2024) noted, the strength of any profession depends upon the degree of commitment of its members. Teachers' job commitment is conceptualized as being multi-dimensional. Thus, teachers' job commitment is the strength of teachers' identification with and involvement in the school organization. It can be viewed as the dedication that teachers believe or perceive toward particular work and the job they carry out in the school.

In addition, the commitment and effectiveness of teachers depend on their motivation, morale and job satisfaction. This implies that teachers' job satisfaction and their job commitment is an important phenomenon for all secondary school teachers, their employers and students at large. For the success of any organization, committed and satisfied human resources are considered as the most important assets of an organization. Thus, teachers' job commitment is an indicator of a teacher's loyalty, professional attachment and job pleasure. It tends to reflect the level of fulfillment; an individual feel from his nature of work and organizational attachment. In other words, it demonstrates an employee's job satisfaction. If employees are satisfied with their job, they have a greater tendency to give better performance and commitment to their job.

In school setting, teachers play vital roles and their importance in the school cannot be over-emphasized. Onwunyi and Mba (2021) maintained that for an organisation to effectively and efficiently function well, the employees and the employers have to work in harmony, better cooperation and understanding in order to increase their performance and commitment. It is therefore worth noting that every organisation needs not only the staff, but also a motivated and support staff to assist in running other services at the organisation and so doing, there is room to make their conditions of service attractive and interesting. Keston (2022) described conditions of service as legal agreements between a service provider or employer and an employee who wants to use or render the service. The person must agree to abide by the terms of service in order to use or offer the service.

Conditions of service are the rules, requirements, and policies an employer and employee agree to abide by during the employee's service to the company. They spell out the rights and obligations of each party. Conditions of service are also known as terms of employment. Afolabi (2023) noted that conditions of service are often found in job postings,

employees' handbooks and company policy manuals. Conditions of service are also spelled out in written employment contracts, but many positions are filled with nothing more than a verbal agreement which can raise legal issues if the employer and employee later disagree about what was promised. For clarity and consistency, and to reduce potential liability, it is important for complete conditions of service to be written down and made available to every employee. Udemezue *et al.* (2023) referred to conditions of service as to the rules, policies and other requirements that an employer and employee agree to uphold during the employee's tenure in the organization.

Owota and Elliot (2022) enumerated conditions of service to include payment of salaries, insurance plan, lay off and termination pay, travel expenses, suggestion awards, medical leave with pay, overtime benefits, promotion, health protection benefits, retirement benefits, educational and house allowance benefits, fringe benefits, annual leave benefits and recognition among others.

Teachers' conditions of service appear unattractive to the teachers. Many teachers have raised their voices severally against their conditions of service. Teachers have bemoaned the way they have been treated shabbily by government, the school authority, the students they teach and even the parents of their students. Chukwueze (2023) asserted that some parents have gone to the school to beat up their wards' teachers on flimsy excuses of maltreatment of their children/wards by such teachers. It is worthy of note that due to the poor conditions of service and inadequate motivation for teachers, their performances on the job have fallen. It seems that many of them have also decided to seek for their fortune elsewhere. It is observed that teachers are not well treated on the job. They seem not well motivated enough to do the job as they should. This has led to brain-drain in our national life, which has inevitably led to the production of semi-illiterates in educational institutions. Due to teachers' poor conditions of service, they do not stay long in the teaching profession. It appears that they see teaching as a stepping stone to obtaining higher-paying job elsewhere due to poor conditions of service of teachers. In this vein, Agah and Yakubu (2024) in buttressing the fact that teachers are ill-treated claimed that it is a pity that teachers who are to see to the total development of the child physically, morally, spiritually and intellectually are treated as underdogs. However, in the course of this study, teachers' conditions of service are narrowed to payment of salaries, promotion, fringe benefits and recognition.

Teachers' salary is a fixed amount of money agreed every year as pay for employees, usually paid directly into their bank account every month. Ileka and Muogbo (2021) noted that salary is a form of payment from an employer to an employee, which might be specified in an employment contract. It is contrasted with piece wages, where each job, hour or other unit is paid separately, rather than on a periodic basis. From the point of view of running a business, salary could also be viewed as the cost of acquiring and retaining human resources for running operations, and is then termed personnel expense or salary expense. Salary is the regular payment by an employer to an employee for employment that is expressed either monthly or annually, but is paid most commonly on a monthly basis, especially to white collar workers, managers, directors and professionals (Obionu *et al.*, 2024). Salary is a fixed amount of money or compensation paid to an employee by an employer in return for work performed. Salary is commonly paid in fixed intervals, for example, monthly payments of one-twelfth of the annual salary. Uke *et al.* (2024) argued that salary is typically determined by comparing market pay rates for people performing similar work in similar industries in the same region. Salary is also determined by leveling the pay rates and salary ranges established by an individual employer. Thus, increase in employees' salary could be as a result of

employees' promotion which seems to enhance their commitment and performance and boosts their morale in the organisation.

Teachers' promotion means the ascension of a teacher to higher ranks. It involves an increase in salary, position, responsibilities, status, and benefits. This aspect of the job drives teachers the most ultimate reward for dedication and loyalty towards the school. Nwankwo and Ilozue (2023) opined that teachers' promotion is an upward mobility of teachers which changes their present position to one that makes them assume greater responsibility. Apart from bringing them more money, promotion has a higher motivating effect and it serves as a mark of recognition of teachers' performance. Hence, promotion can be seen as a feedback that the teachers have performed well. Promotion is the elevation to a higher job accompanied by increased pay and privileges (Obi & Ebelechukwu, 2024). It is an upward advancement of an employee in an organisation, which commands better pay, better status, higher opportunities, higher responsibilities and better work environment. Promotion provides motivation and job satisfaction to all personnel. Continuing, Obi and Ebelechukwu (2024) noted that quite often, industrial unrest, frustration and negative feeling among the employees are on account of matters concerned with promotion and employees express their feelings and thoughts through involving them in making decisions in the organisation. When teachers' promotion is not promptly practiced, it may lead to poor commitment of teachers but school principals can use other means to motivate and boost teachers' job commitment like regular fringe benefits.

Teachers' fringe benefits are additional compensation provided to teachers that is not directly related with their salary or wages for the performance of a specific service. Some fringe benefits such as social security and health insurance are required by law, while others are voluntarily provided by the employer. Examples of optional fringe benefits include free breakfast and lunch, employee stock options, transportation benefits, retirement planning services, childcare, and education assistance, among others. Fringe benefits are a form of pay, often from employers to employees, and considered compensation for services beyond the employees' normal rate of pay. They can be made in the form of property, services, cash, or cash equivalents (Osang *et al.*, 2023). Teachers' fringe benefits are regarded as the collection of various benefits provided by an employer, which are exempted from taxation as long as certain conditions are met. Thus, teachers' fringe benefits vary according to schools and can come in different forms like medical and dental insurance, use of a company's car, housing allowance, educational assistance, sick pay, research grant, transport allowance, examination supervision / teaching practice allowance and employees' discounts among others. These allowances should be paid regularly to spur teachers in their commitment to duties. Teachers' fringe benefits can also come in form of praise, rewards and recognition.

Recognition occurs when teachers' employers share teachers' good work and achievement with them and even with extended audience. Chukwunedum (2022) noted that appreciation and recognition are good indications that the behaviour of the teacher is valued. They further observed that it is common in a workplace for employers to get more of the employees' behaviour they recognise and appreciate. They make teachers to fulfill task and their dreams. They are capable of eliciting good work performance needed to maintain commitment in the school. A principal's quick feedback after observing a teacher teach good lesson, after assessing his/her school records or consistently being punctual to school, will help school administrators maintain what can be described as "psychological contract". Teachers' recognitions can be as candid as a pat-on-the-back and a genuine compliment. It

can also be as simple as a ‘thank you’, praises, applause or a friendly greeting at work (Kaegon & Okeke, 2023).

Furthermore, teachers whose needs, goals and aspirations are thwarted by the organization, develop feelings of low self-worth, become apathetic, disinterested, frustrated and tend to withhold self-commitment to the work. Thus, the way conditions of service in public secondary schools are provided and managed might influence teachers’ feelings and interest towards their job and commitment to the school. In public secondary schools in Anambra State, it is unfortunate that most secondary school teachers are subjected to work under conditions where promotion, payment of salaries and other entitlements are unduly delayed; where teachers are inadequately motivated, they will be less committed and unsatisfied to give their best at work to promote performance as well as enhance moral development of their students. It is on this background that the researchers sought to investigate how conditions of service and predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

It is a reality that teachers are the instrument through which educational objectives can be achieved. If teachers are properly motivated by the conditions of service and support services, they might be committed and satisfied to give their best at work to promote performance as well as enhance moral development of their students. This is due to poor conditions of services prevailing in public secondary schools. The teachers in public secondary schools have to seek for alternative means to make ends meet, causing divided attention, absenteeism from school, irregular attendance to class, lack of concentration, dissatisfaction, low commitment to work among others. These lapses are maybe as a result of poor conditions of services and inadequate teachers’ support services which is a negative signals coming from the system over low commitment of teachers. This seemed to mean that school management is not working up to expectations. It appears school management does not effectively and efficiently provide support services to teachers nor honour the conditions of service in areas of payment of salaries, adequate promotion, payment of fringe benefits, good recognition, conducive work environment, regular in-service training and building good teamwork among teachers. Against the background that, the researchers sought to find out how conditions of service predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine conditions of service as predictors of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

1. payment of salaries predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. promotion predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. fringe benefits predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. recognition predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does payment of salaries predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of promotion on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. How do fringe benefits predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
4. What is the predictive value of recognition on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Payment of salaries does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Promotion does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Fringe benefits do not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. Recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

The design of the study was a correlational research design. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six education zones in Anambra State was used for the study. The sample of 660 teachers was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection: Conditions of Service Questionnaire (COSQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ). The instruments are structured in three sections namely A, B and C Section A deals with the personal data of the respondents, while section B and C dealt with COSQ and TJCQ.

Conditions of Service Questionnaire (COSQ) which was structured by the researcher measured teachers' conditions of service in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument COSQ contained 40-items spread across four Clusters 'A-D.' Cluster 'A' elicited information on payment of salaries with 10-items; Cluster 'B' elicited information on promotion with 10-items; Cluster 'C' elicits information on fringe benefits with 10-items; and Cluster 'D' elicited information on recognition with 10-items. These items were placed on 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The range of scores was weighted as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJSQ) as structured by the researcher measured job commitment of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument TJCQ has 15-items with a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point).

The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The experts were requested to review and critique the various items of the instruments in terms of relevance,

clarity, and appropriateness of language and response patterns as they relate to the study. Their criticisms, suggestions and modifications were incorporated into the relevant items to give the instruments their present structure and content. On the other hand, construct validation was carried out with the help SPSS v.25. Construct validity of the instruments for components loading eight factors was explored using Principal Component Analysis approach. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) as a measure of sampling adequacy to conduct the Principal Component Analysis was obtained as 0.891. The reliability was determined by administering copies of the questionnaire to 30 teachers in public secondary schools in Enugu State. The instruments were administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of five research assistants. Out of 660 copies of the instrument administered, 628(95%) of the instrument were correctly completed and returned, while 32(5%) were either misplaced or not correctly filled. Simple regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

For Regression Coefficient (r)

- + Sign = Positive Prediction
- Sign = Negative Prediction

The negative sign means a negative coefficient which indicates a negative prediction or correlation between variables, while a positive sign means a positive coefficient which indicates a positive prediction or correlation between variables.

For p-value when

- Sig. (2-tailed) < .05: Reject H_0 and Accept H_1
- Sig. (2-tailed) > .05: Do not reject H_0

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of 0.05 the null hypotheses was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: How does payment of salaries predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with payment of salary as it predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	31.364	5.758	
Payment of Salary	.782	.244	.773
R	.773		
R^2	.624		
Adj. R^2	.584		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that payment of salary positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.773$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.624 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was highly strong. This implies that 62% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers'

payment of salary. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.584 indicating that 58% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' payment of salary). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of payment of salary is highly strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.773$) showed that teachers' payment of salary is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increase in teachers' payment of salary led to 0.773 (77%) increase in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' payment of salary on their job commitment means that teachers' job commitment highly depends on the regular and prompt payment of teachers' salary in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of promotion on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with promotion as it predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	29.371	6.315	
Promotion	.779	.249	.751
R	.751		
R^2	.613		
Adj. R^2	.576		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that promotion positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.751$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.613 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was highly strong. This implies that 61% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' promotion. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.576 indicating that 58% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' promotion). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of promotion is highly strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. In addition, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.751$) showed that teachers' promotion is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit step up in teachers' promotion led to 0.751(75%) increase in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' promotion on their job commitment means that teachers' job commitment highly depends on prompt promotion of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: How do fringe benefits predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis with fringe benefit as predictor of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	27.421	6.948	
Fringe Benefits	.656	.337	.618
R	.618		
R ²	.532		
Adj. R ²	.509		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 indicated that fringe benefits positively predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.618$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.532 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 53% of the variations in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers’ fringe benefits. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.509 indicating that 51% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers’ job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers’ fringe benefits). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of fringe benefits is moderately strong in determining the teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. However, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.618$) showed that teachers’ fringe benefits is a positive predictor of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increase in teachers’ fringe benefits led to 0.613(61%) increase in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers’ fringe benefits on their job commitment means that teachers’ job commitment moderately depends on the regular and adequate provision of fringe benefits to teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 4: What is the predictive value of recognition on teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 4: Summary of simple regression analysis with recognition as predictor of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	25.271	7.154	
Recognition	.552	.367	.524
R	.524		
R ²	.476		
Adj. R ²	.418		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 indicated that recognition positively predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.524$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.476 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 48% of the variations in teachers’ job commitment in

public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' recognition. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.418 indicating that 42% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' recognition). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of recognition is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. More so, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.524$) showed that teachers' recognition is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit improvement in teachers' recognition led to 0.524 (52%) increase in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' recognition on their job commitment means that teachers' job commitment moderately depends on the adequate provision of teachers' recognition and appreciation of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₁: Payment of salary does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with payment of salary does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	31.364	5.758		27.524	.000
Payment of Salary	.782	.244	.773	23.061	.000
R	.773				
R^2	.624				
Adj. R^2	.584				
F	42.137				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 5 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.773 while the R^2 is 0.624 and Adjust R^2 is 0.584. The F-ratio associated with regression is 42.137, the t-test is 23.061 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that payment of salary does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that payment of salary significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₂: Promotion does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with promotion does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized	t-	p-
	B	β	β	value	value
Constant	29.371	6.315		24.529	.000
Promotion	.779	.249	.751	21.664	.000
R	.751				
R ²	.613				
Adj. R ²	.576				
F	37.458				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 6 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.751 while the R² is 0.613 and Adjust R² is 0.576. The F-ratio associated with regression is 37.458, the t-test is 21.664 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that promotion does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that promotion significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₃: Fringe benefits do not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 7: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with fringe benefits do not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized	t-	p-
	β	β	β	value	value
Constant	27.421	6.948		23.641	.000
Fringe Benefits	.656	.337	.618	20.546	.000
R	.618				
R ²	.532				
Adj. R ²	.509				
F	33.125				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 7 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.618 while the R² is 0.532 and Adjust R² is 0.509. The F-ratio associated with regression is 33.125, the t-test is 20.546 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that fringe benefits do not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that fringe benefits significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₄: Recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 8: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized	t-	p-
	β	β	β	value	value
Constant	25.271	7.154		22.975	.000
Recognition	.552	.367	.524	19.143	.000
R	.524				
R ²	.476				
Adj. R ²	.418				
F	30.427				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 8 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.524 while the R² is 0.476 and Adjust R² is 0.418. The F-ratio associated with regression is 30.427, the t-test is 19.143 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that recognition significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

Findings on how payment of salary predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that payment of salary positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This could be due to the fact that receiving a regular salary can give teachers the confidence to take on more responsibility and feel more secure and committed in their role in school. This is in line with Obionu *et al.* (2024a) that payment of salaries positively and significantly related to teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent. Similarly, Uke *et al.* (2024) found that not giving salaries in time highly make workers dissatisfied leading to poor performance. Afolabi (2023) re-affirmed that payment of teachers' monetary rewards affected teachers' job performance. The findings of the study indicated that irregular payment of salaries reduced teachers' moral in discharge of their duties as form masters, house masters, their commitment and dedication to work. This implies that irregular payment of salaries affects teachers' attitude to work. This corroborates Sunoma *et al.* (2022) that payment of salary has great influence on teachers' attitude to work. The findings also showed that irregular payment of salaries discouraged teachers in discipline of students and regular writing of lesson plan. As a result of that, teachers skipped classes or lessons. It was discovered from the findings that irregular payment of salaries makes work boring, uninteresting and reluctant to teachers.

Findings on how promotion predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that promotion positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This could be due to the fact that teachers in public secondary schools look forward to a time of compensation for the effort they put into the school system and one the ways of meeting this expectation is through promotion. Nwankwo and Ilozue (2023) agreed with this position when he opined that teachers who receive regular promotion are always in high spirit at work. Obi and Ebelechukwu (2024) added that teachers' promotion positively relates with teachers' job commitment in any formal organization. Teachers who put in their best for the achievement of the goals and objectives of the school expect to be promoted as a way of compensating

them for the effort invested into the school. Thus, when promotion of teachers is given top priority, teachers are likely to be motivated which can bring about job satisfaction. This finding supports the contention of Obiekwe *et al.* (2024) who concluded that a significant relationship existed between regular promotion and job satisfaction. The implication of this finding is that prompt and timely promotion of teachers will lead to job satisfaction

Findings on how fringe benefits predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that fringe benefits positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is expected that all things being equal, teachers' job commitment should relate positively and significantly to adequate provision of fringe benefits to teachers in schools. When the teachers are not adequately motivated through fringe benefits, it affects other aspects of the teachers' life. This is in line with Udemzue *et al.* (2023) that adequate payment of fringe benefits increased the level of teachers' job commitment and performance in schools. The findings revealed that inadequate availability of free accommodation for teachers in school does not improve their punctuality to work, irregular payment of retirement benefits to retire teachers, death benefits to deceased teachers and none provision of welfare packages does not boost teachers' performance by improving their commitment and dedication to work. In the same vein, Agah and Yakubu (2024) confirmed that non-payment of fringe benefits such as health protection and retirement benefits have negative impact on teachers' job commitment. Non-payment of leave bonus and lack of incentives for teachers reduce their moral and make them reluctant to their work. This implies that non-payment of leave bonus and other incentives affects teachers' attitude to work. This corroborates with Ahmed (2024) that irregular payment of fringe benefits such as leave bonus for teachers have great negative influence on teachers' attitude to work. Teachers can only show commitment to the school when they have the feeling that their needs are taken seriously.

Findings on how recognition predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that recognition positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Recognition is not just about making teachers feel good, but also makes them feel valued and drives them to do their best in school. Teachers work harder and are more dedicated to their job when motivated through praising them to do so. This finding lend credence to the findings of Ikedimma and Okorji (2023) that, irrespective of gender, teachers are more productive, satisfied with their job and healthier, physically, emotionally, socially, and academically, when motivated by either words of praise for harder or recognition through gifts. The finding is also in line with Chukwunedum (2022) that teachers who do not feel supported with at least words of encouragement and recognition are less motivated to do their best in the classroom. In line with this, Kaegon and Okere (2023) pointed out that administrators should not see themselves as the 'boss' but as a 'facilitator'. Continuing, an administrator who sees himself as a facilitator always involves his staff in decision-making and showers them with words of praises for good job thereby enhancing teachers job satisfaction and commitment in schools.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the findings, the study concluded that the honouring of teachers' conditions of service positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Government should improve the monetary reward for teachers to enable them afford their needs. Apart from that, there should be prompt payment of salaries including all allowances accruing to teachers: salaries should be paid regularly as at when due. Also, the practice of owing teachers' salaries for some months or percentage payment should be stopped as that has destroyed teachers' commitment and dedication to work.
2. The state government should promote teachers as and when due as a way of motivating the teachers to continue with their good job performances and commitment for the benefit of the students in the teaching and learning process in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Government should intensify her efforts in providing fringe benefits such as health protection, retirement package, free accommodation, transportation, leave bonus, pension, cash bonus, and other welfare packages for teachers that will encourage them to create a sense of commitment and dedication leading to an improved performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. School principals should adopt daily recognition of teachers to encourage them for their hard work and applaud them on a regular basis in order to boost their morale to sustain and improve their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

References

- Afolabi, C. Y. (2023). Conditions of service of teachers as correlates of motivation in secondary schools in Ado and Efon Local Government Areas, Ekiti State. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 1(1), 89-93. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.1n.1p.89>.
- Agah, P. M., & Yakubu, N. (2024). Impact of conditions of service on teachers' job performance in senior secondary school in Gombi Education Zone, Adamawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, VIII(II), 2236-2246. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS>.
- Ahmed, A. A. (2024). Effects of irregular payment of teachers' salaries and provision of fringe benefits on implementation of curriculum in public senior secondary schools in North-Central, Nigeria. *African Journal of Humanities and Contemporary Education Research*, 14(1), 65-77. <https://doi.org/10.62154/t2na6223>.
- Chukwueze, A. C. (2023). Influence of support system on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Abia State. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research*, 11(2), 100-111. <https://seahipaj.org/journals-ci/june-2023/IJISSER/full/IJISSER-J-13-2023.pdf>.
- Chukwunedum, S. I. (2022). Motivation and teachers' job satisfaction for improved job commitment of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 05(04), 10-17. [file:///C:/Users/pc/Downloads/585-Article%20Text-2116-1-10-20220428%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/pc/Downloads/585-Article%20Text-2116-1-10-20220428%20(1).pdf). <https://ajemates.org/index.php/ajemates/article/view/335/295>. <https://www.openjournals.ijaar.org/index.php/ijaar/article/view/433>.
- Kaegon, L. E.S., & Okere, N. V. (2023). Workplace best practices and teachers' job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 9(4), 61-70. <https://seahipaj.org/journals-ci/dec-2023/IJISSHR/full/IJISSHR-D-4-2023.pdf>.
- Keston, B. (2022). Impact of conditions of service on the performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kogi State. *Unpublished Master's Thesis*, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Nwankwo, I. N., & Ilozue, E. C. (2023). Principals' promotion strategies for improving teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. *African Journal of Educational Management, Teaching and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 10(1), 144-150.
- Obi, E.F., & Ebelechukwu, C. (2024). Principals' human resource management practices as predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *African Journal of Educational Management, Teaching and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 11(1), 174-180. <https://ajemates.org/index.php/ajemates/article/view/388>.
- Obionu, U. A., Ughamadu, U., & Obiagwu, C. (2024a). Staff remuneration as a correlate of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 10(3), 39-54.

- Onwunyi, U. M., & Mba, A. O. (2021). Work environment and employee performance in the public service: A study of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Anambra State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Political Science and Administration*, 9(1), 39-56. <https://doi.org/10.2107/6342-323>.
- Osang, W. O., Osang, A. W., & Akpama, S. I. (2023). Prompt payment of salaries and fringe benefits as determinants of teachers' productivity in public secondary schools of Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI)*, 12(10), 4413-4423. <https://www.tojq.net/index.php/journal/article/view/8507/6038>.
- Thahir, M., Komariah, A., Kurniady, D. A., Suharto, N., Kurniatun, T. C., Widiawati, W., & Nurlatifah, S. (2022). Professional development and job satisfaction on teaching performance in Indonesia. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S4), 2507-2522. <https://doi.org/10.21744/lingcure.v5nS4.2046>.
- Udemezue, A. I., Ufoaroh, E. T., & Chike, P. (2023). Welfare packages and staff performance in Polytechnics in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 06(09), 6236-6245. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V6-i9-14>.
- Uke, A. F., Otu, E. P., Abel, V. E., & Udom, V. A. (2024). Teachers' job satisfaction indicators and job commitment in private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development*, 12(2), 11-25. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijeld.2013/vol12n21125>.